

Do transcription factor-based receptors moonlight as enzymes?

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How cells and organelles communicate is a fundamental question in biology. Proteins can exhibit moonlighting function in different organelles and receptors can also exhibit duality in sensing.^{1,2} Likewise, several transcription factors can act as receptors and major examples include retinoic acid, vitamin D and estrogen receptors.³⁻⁵ But then a question arises, can transcription factors (without any explicit domains for catalytic activity) can also act as enzymes? For instance, let's consider heme-binding transcription factors such as bacterial CooA, *Drosophila* E75, mammalian REV-ERB β and NPAS2, all of which can act as gasoreceptors.⁶⁻⁹ These transcription factors bind and sense gas (solute) such as carbon monoxide or nitric oxide primarily via heme. But then what stops these transcription factors from acting as enzymes via the heme group? If it is all about the local microenvironment of the amino acid residues near the heme, how stable are these microenvironment when these transcription factors can bind various factors or face varying environmental conditions in a cell which the transcription factors must traverse or gets localized into?¹⁰ Will such local cellular environment-induced changes or binding partners can enable a switch of these transcription factors to act as enzymes? As gasoreceptors are likely also to be other than hemoproteins, addressing this question will be essential to understand some of the complexities of gasocrine signaling.

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